

CCxTrust: Confidential Computing Platform Based on TEE and TPM Collaborative Trust

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Abstract—Confidential computing ensures data and code security in multi-party collaborative computing based on hardware TEE. However, it is difficult to fully guarantee the security of complex confidential virtual machine (CVM) environments such as confidential AI applications, relying solely on a single TEE root of trust (RoT) with significant side-channel attacks and system vulnerabilities.

This paper proposes CCxTrust (Confidential Computing with Trust), a novel collaborative multi-hardware RoTs scheme for a confidential computing platform. CCxTrust combines the black-box RoT of CPU-TEE with the flexible white-box RoT of TPM to establish CVM's collaborative trust framework. With TEE and TPM together, it implements a parallel independent RoT for Measurement, a collaborative RoT for Report using composite attestation, and a TPM-based RoT for Storage. We further design a confidential TPM and a composite attestation protocol of TEE and TPM to ensure the CVM environment's high trustworthiness. The protocols are proven secure under the PCL security model and the Proverif formal security analysis tool.

We implement the CCxTrust prototype on a confidential computing server with AMD SEV-SNP and TPM chip, only requiring minimal changes to the TPM and guest kernel. In our benchmark, TEE and TPM composite attestation demonstrate 20.4% performance improvement over independent spliced attestation. Confidential AI application with CCxTrust has 6% performance overhead compared to native AI inference. To our knowledge, CCxTrust is the first practical work combining TPM and TEE collaboration to improve security resilience against a single point of trust in a TEE environment.

Index Terms—TEE, TPM, Confidential Computing, Root of Trust, Collaborative Trust, Composite Attestation

I. INTRODUCTION

With the widespread adoption of private clouds in enterprise core services, data security and privacy protection have become central concerns in private cloud deployments. In particular, confidential virtual machines (CVMs) like AMD SEV, Intel TDX, and ARM CCA leverage Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8] to enhance the security of data and workloads in virtualized environments [9], [10].

To minimize the attack surface and provide a more secure isolation environment, existing CVMs adopt different trust models based on specific hardware and architectures [11], [12], [13]. Unfortunately, existing CVM solutions suffer from

fragmented trust models and limited user control. In private cloud settings, where all components are typically owned by the same organization, current models still rely on a single, vendor-specific root of trust (RoT) designed for public clouds. This undermines user demands for autonomy, verifiability, and high-assurance security in private deployments. In private clouds, users not only care about data confidentiality during processing, but also demand system-wide integrity, key sovereignty, and consistent trust across heterogeneous hardware. However, existing CVM solutions focus primarily on intra-TEE protection, lacking effective cross-hardware and cross-component trust coordination. This prevents users from centrally managing and verifying diverse trust anchors within local environments, further exacerbating trust fragmentation and operational complexity.

Moreover, current CVM solutions offer limited guarantees before TEE initialization and cannot fully ensure the integrity of workloads within the TEE. While some schemes [14] introduce virtual TPM (vTPM) to provide a runtime trust root, vTPM operates inside the CVM and lacks binding to a confidential computing hardware platform, unlike independent hardware. They also lack strong cryptographic binding to the platform and persistent secure storage, making them unsuitable for scenarios involving reboot or migration. These limitations restrict their effectiveness in multi-node or long-lived cloud deployments. Therefore, relying solely on TEE and vTPM mechanisms is insufficient to meet the demands for secure initialization, persistent trust roots, key control, and end-to-end verifiability in private cloud settings.

Additionally, the trust model of existing CVM solutions mainly depends on the RoT provided by cloud providers or platform vendors. It offers users limited involvement in trust establishment or verification. This asymmetric trust model is especially problematic in high-privacy scenarios, such as confidential AI, where sensitive data and valuable models must remain protected throughout training and inference [15], [16]. However, users lack visibility and control over the cloud execution environment and cannot independently verify the integrity of their computations. Thus, despite the use of TEEs, a trust gap remains due to the absence of user-controlled trust mechanisms.

To address the issues above, we propose CCxTrust, a confidential computing platform based on the collaborative trust of TEE and TPM. Confidential computing platforms incorporate multiple independent hardware RoT, such as CPU-TEE and TPM. CCxTrust introduces a novel confidential computing trust model that unifies multi-hardware RoTs and leverages

the synergistic trust mechanism between TEE and TPM to enhance trust transparency and user autonomy. Bridging the existing trust gaps, it enables a verifiable trust framework across platforms and cloud environments.

In CCxTrust, we first proposed a collaborative Root of Trust (CRoT) mechanism combining TEE and TPM. The Measurement Roots of Trust (RTM) for TEE and TPM operate independently in parallel, ensuring platform integrity. Their Report Roots of Trust (RTR) jointly produces a composite attestation report, enabling unified remote attestation. The Storage Root of Trust (RTS), provided solely by TPM, protects cryptographic keys used within the TEE. To enable secure and efficient TPM usage in cloud environments, we design a hardware-based Confidential TPM (cTPM) that runs in a CVM. Acting as a TPM Device CVM, the cTPM addresses the limitations of directly passing through a hardware TPM (hTPM) and supports persistent storage inside the CVM. To resist binding attacks, we establish a binding mechanism between the cTPM and the hTPM, tailored for cloud scenarios. Upon cTPM initialization, a trusted channel is established via ECDH negotiation between TEE and hTPM, securing key provisioning and composite attestation. The cTPM provides user-controlled RoT services, decoupled from the cloud provider’s trust, and exposes standard TPM functionality to upper-layer applications. To support globally verifiable attestation, CCxTrust designs a composite protocol that merges the TEE-generated static trust chain with the TPM-generated dynamic trust chain, ensuring the uniqueness and integrity of the attestation and preventing forgery or report splicing.

In summary, this paper makes the following contributions:

- **New Architecture:** This paper presents CCxTrust, a collaborative multi-hardware RoT scheme for confidential computing. It introduces an independent RTM, a composited RTR, and a complementary RTS to support multi-layer anomaly detection and enhanced fault tolerance, thereby strengthening CVM trustworthiness and resilience.
- **Innovative Protocol and Security:** This paper designs and implements a composite attestation protocol for confidential computing platforms based on TEE and TPM, enhancing both security and efficiency in remote attestation. The protocol mitigates identity forgery and report splicing attacks, outperforming traditional schemes in this regard. Its security is formally verified with PCL and ProVerif, ensuring attestation correctness, integrity, and report verifiability.
- **Security Foundation:** Designed a TPM Device CVM that enables secure access to hardware TPM, offering hardware-grade security guarantees. This design allows scalable and trusted TPM services across multiple CVMs in a confidential computing platform, without relying on the cloud provider’s trust.
- **Implementation and Evaluation:** We implement a CCxTrust prototype and evaluate it on a confidential computing platform using AMD SEV-SNP and a TPM chip. The results demonstrate that CCxTrust is a feasible,

Fig. 1: The architecture overview of mainstream CVM platforms.

efficient, and scalable solution. Composite attestation improves efficiency by 20.4% over independent splicing, with only 6% overhead for confidential AI inference compared to native inference.

II. BACKGROUND

Confidential Virtual Machines. Confidential Virtual Machines (CVMs) provide a confidential computing abstraction at the virtual machine level [17]. The architecture of CVMs is shown in Figure 1. It can be divided into two parts: a trusted guest domain and an untrusted host domain.

CVM platforms isolate guest private memory from the host using hardware-assisted encryption and register protections. As shown in Figure 1, guest memory is divided into encrypted private (blue) and unencrypted shared (gray) regions. Private memory is transparently encrypted on writes and decrypted on reads [18]. For external devices, authenticated devices interact via shared memory over encrypted channels, while unauthorized access is blocked. During initialization, the trusted hardware and/or firmware generate a launch measurement that reflects the basic execution environment. This is then signed and submitted to the user for verification. However, it excludes cloud-native components. To provide runtime integrity, some platforms introduce vTPM within the CVM. Yet, since vTPM depends on the underlying TEE as its RoT and runs entirely inside the guest, its trust ultimately depends on the CVM and host. An attacker could forge attestation by combining a valid vTPM QUOTE with a Guest REPORT from another platform, bypassing verification. This exposes fragmented trust boundaries in current confidential computing systems.

Trusted Platform Module. The Trusted Platform Module (TPM), as a cryptographic coprocessor, offers a standardized, hardware-backed security solution [21], [22], [23], [24]. It serves as a foundational component for establishing new security technologies, fundamentally safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of computing platforms [25].

For instance, AMD processors utilize the fTPM for secure key storage and cryptographic operations; however, its security can be compromised by physical attacks, such as voltage fault injection, which may lead to key extraction [26]. CoCoTPM [20] introduces a vTPM for each VM in confidential computing environments, supporting use cases such as integrity measurement, disk encryption, and key sealing. The SvTPM [19] offers a vTPM solution with hardware isolation. Addi-

TABLE I: Feature comparison of CCxTrust-cTPM and other TEE-based vTPMs

Program	RoT	Hardware Mod.	Persistent Storage	Secure Boot	Anti-Forgery	Anti-Rollback	Secure Comm.	Node Binding
SvTPM [19]	Intel	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	SSL	1:1
CocoTPM [20]	OCA	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	SSL	1:n
SVSM-vTPM [14]	AMD	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	Custom	1:1
CCxTrust-cTPM	hTPM	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	ECDH	1:n

tionally, SvTPM features persistent storage, protecting against rollback attacks and unauthorized access or tampering.

Table I summarizes the key distinctions between our proposed CCxTrust-cTPM and conventional TEE-based vTPM solutions. Rather than functioning as a TEE-based vTPM solution or a basic TPM-based key manager, CCxTrust integrates TEE and TPM in a mutually attesting architecture to strengthen the system’s RoT. It offers hardware-backed persistent storage, composite attestation, and robust key management with rollback protection and report anti-forgery. These features enhance security in private cloud environments, while its fine-grained workload monitoring augments TEE integrity mechanisms such as RMP.

Trust Model. The Root of Trust (RoT) forms the foundational security basis of confidential computing platforms. It enables the establishment of a TEE, protects cryptographic keys, performs integrity measurements, and provides assurance for remote attestation.

Remote attestation aims to convey the platform’s trust chain to verifiers for independent security evaluation. The IETF’s Remote Attestation Procedures (RATS) [27], [28] serve as the standard for many implementations. Intel SGX supports EPID [29] and DCAP [30], but both depend heavily on Intel’s centralized services, limiting user autonomy. Opera [31] and Mage [32] propose decentralization via open attestation infrastructure and peer identity delegation. However, SGX attestation remains vulnerable to side-channel attacks that can leak signing keys [8]. MATEE [33] addresses this by binding attestation to a TPM-based RoT immune to such attacks. In AMD SEV, outdated firmware and design flaws allow attestation bypass [34]. SEV-SNP [2] mitigates this by enforcing firmware integrity, while SVSM [14] enhances dynamic trust by introducing a temporary vTPM-based attestation flow.

Current CVM platforms are limited by hardware-bound, single-vendor RoTs (e.g., Intel, AMD), restricting user control and exposing systems to opaque, vendor-managed key and policy enforcement. While TEEs provide strong runtime isolation, they lack user-facing interfaces. In contrast, TPMs offer transparent RoTs supporting key management, integrity measurement, and attestation [35], [36], [37], [38]. Combining TPM’s user-controllable services with TEE’s secure execution enables a layered trust model to strengthen platform security.

Some high-performance computing platforms have adopted a dual-root trust architecture that integrates both TEE and TPM. For instance, the NVIDIA A100 AI server platform [39] can be deployed with AMD SEV-SNP as the runtime protection foundation for CVMs, while simultaneously leveraging a hardware TPM as the platform’s RoT for secure boot and persistent key storage.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

A. Design Goals

CCxTrust aims to establish a collaborative trust architecture for confidential computing by integrating TEE and TPM, enabling a user-controlled trust model in private cloud environments. By eliminating dependence on a single platform vendor, it provides a unified RoT co-protected by TPM and TEE. Designed for cross-platform compatibility (x86, ARM, RISC-V), CCxTrust requires minimal changes to the software stack and remains transparent to user-space applications within the CVM, while offering strong security guarantees.

B. Challenges

To achieve the unified RoT in the CCxTrust, the following key issues need to be addressed.

Q1: How to build a trust system controlled by the user?

Current TEE systems typically depend on root CAs issued by device manufacturers, placing users in a passive position within the trust hierarchy. This indirect trust model limits users’ ability to verify or control their own trust roots, posing challenges for multi-tenant deployments in private clouds and scenarios requiring high autonomy and assurance.

Q2: How to bridge the technical gap between TEE and TPM?

TEE and TPM serve distinct roles in security—TEE ensures isolated execution, while TPM offers secure key storage and integrity verification. However, their collaboration faces multi-layered technical gaps. TEE cannot directly access hardware TPM due to IOMMU constraints, and lacks native persistent storage, unlike TPM. A critical challenge is securely integrating TPM within TEE as a RoT for key protection and integrity verification while establishing a verifiable trust chain between TEE and TPM.

Q3: How can the security of sensitive data within CVMs be ensured?

In confidential computing platforms, CVMs are responsible for processing highly sensitive data, but they face threats from multiple stack layers. While memory encryption supported by TEEs can protect data in use, the protections it provides are limited in the runtime environment. Ensuring runtime integrity relies on dynamic measurements and remote attestation, but maintaining the authenticity of these measurements while preventing tampering, replay, and partial reporting remains a key challenge. Therefore, attesting to the full lifecycle of the CVM environment remains an open issue, requiring robust and scalable solutions.

C. Architecture and High-Level Design

To address secure interconnection across large-scale heterogeneous nodes, we propose CCxTrust, a collaborative trusted computing platform integrating TEE and TPM. As shown in

Fig. 2: The overall architecture of CCxTrust

Figure 2a, the physical architecture connects CPU TEE and TPM chips via the motherboard’s physical PCIe/SPI/LPC bus, while TPM chips link to PCH (Platform Controller Hub) on the computer motherboard. The system architecture (Figure 2b) features heterogeneous RoT (e.g., TEE, TPM) connected via encrypted PCIe links. Both the kernel and hypervisor are assumed to be untrusted. A privileged CVM hosts the cTPM, providing TPM functionality to user CVMs. User CVMs are protected by TEE-based runtime isolation, which hides their internal state even from the platform. While user workloads remain untrusted, the cTPM complements TEE protection by offering integrity and key management services. Secure communication between user CVMs and the cTPM is established via mutual attestation, after which TPM services are accessed through an in-guest Agent.

To establish a robust, user-controlled trust foundation, CCxTrust introduces three key mechanisms: (1) **S1: Collaborative Root of Trust** (§ IV-A), which establishes a TEE- and TPM-based CRoT comprising RTM, RTR, and RTS, enabling user-controlled unified trust through independent measurement, composite attestation, and TPM-backed secure storage; (2) **S2: Confidential TPM** (§ IV-B), enabling secure TPM access within CVMs by binding hTPM and vTPM to platform hardware, and enhancing key hierarchy protection via a built-in timestamping mechanism; and (3) **S3: Composite Attestation** (§ IV-C), which integrates static measurements from TEE and dynamic runtime evidence from TPM into a co-signed, unified attestation report, strengthening end-to-end trustworthiness across the system.

D. Threat Model

Similar to traditional CVM threat models, the TCB comprises TEE-protected virtual machines, on-chip hardware, and the TPM. We assume that workloads inside CVMs do not intentionally leak sensitive data. The adversary is powerful, with physical access to server hardware (e.g., memory, peripherals, buses) and full control over the software stack, including the hypervisor and host kernel. This enables image

tampering, firmware rollback, and CVM impersonation. The attacker may also intercept, modify, or block communication between the hTPM and cTPM, and exploit guest kernel vulnerabilities to compromise the CVM or target the cTPM from an untrusted VM. During attestation, attackers may forge reports by spoofing components or constructing incomplete composite evidence to deceive verifiers. Denial-of-service and side-channel attacks on the TEE are out of scope, as they are mitigated by orthogonal approaches [40], [41], [42].

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Collaborative Root of Trust

In modern private cloud and confidential computing environments, security and privacy are critical concerns. CVMs enforce the confidentiality and integrity of data through hardware memory encryption and integrity checks while also leveraging other peripherals, such as TPM, to enhance system security further. However, different hardware platforms typically rely on their own independent root Certificate Authorities (CAs) for trust authentication, resulting in a lack of unified trust relationships across platforms. Moreover, the key management system within a CVM lacks a bottom-up protection mechanism, making it difficult to secure internal data and operations within the CVM effectively.

To unify diverse Roots of Trust (RoTs) and enhance secure coordination among heterogeneous TEE, we propose a Multi-Root Trust System centrally managed by an Owner Certificate Authority (OCA). The OCA functions as both the TEE’s OCA and the TPM’s Privacy CA, establishing a TPM-protected key derivation framework based on a unique *MasterSecret* per node. When a new node joins, it submits its TEE measurements and identity credentials for OCA validation. Upon successful authentication, the OCA issues a *Node_cert* and securely injects the *MasterSecret* into the node’s TPM, protected by the TPM, and used to derive keys. This enables scalable key derivation and secure communication within the cluster. The OCA also performs periodic audits, certificate

renewal, and secret rotation to maintain cluster-wide trust continuity and mitigate long-term risks.

In virtualized environments, trust management for CVMs is a key challenge. Traditional architectures rely on a single vendor-provided RTR, which covers hardware and firmware but lacks runtime protection. While integrating TPM extends trust coverage, it also introduces risks like forged attestations and unchecked report concatenation, potentially compromising system integrity (see Figure 1). Thus, this paper proposes a collaborative roots of trust (CRoT) mechanism based on TPM and TEE.

Within the same computing environment, TEE and TPM work together to establish a CRoT, integrating key confidential computing functionalities such as secure boot, trust chain construction, key management, remote attestation, and sealed storage, among others.

- **RTM: TEE & TPM Parallel Independence**

The RTM is independently managed by the TEE and TPM to ensure system integrity and trustworthiness. The TEE measures hardware, firmware, and the runtime environment, emphasizing the secure boot and loading of the CVM’s security components. Meanwhile, the TPM measures the CVM’s launch and runtime workloads, capturing critical data during initialization and performing dynamic measurements throughout the operation.

For the RTM, we have designed and extended the CVM trust chain architecture based on TPM, proposing a three-stage collaborative measurement for CVMs based on TEE and TPM. This method ensures the entire trust chain of the CVM from launch to runtime, protecting key components and workloads.

Stage 1: Static Measurement of Host System Components. Before launching a CVM, the system measures critical host components, such as the hypervisor, host kernel, and virtualization services, to ensure they have not been tampered with. The hTPM extends and verifies these measurements before launching, ensuring the host environment’s integrity. **Stage 2: CVM Launch Measurement.** During CVM launch, TEE verifies key elements (e.g., firmware, initrd, rootfs, images) by measuring their integrity and origin. The *Launch Measurement* is recorded for remote attestation, ensuring the foundational components of the CVM are secure. **Stage 3: Runtime Measurement of Confidential Workloads.** After CVM is launched, cTPM monitors the integrity of sensitive applications and data within the CVM. The system continuously performs integrity checks on workloads and responds to anomalies to prevent sensitive information leaks.

Overall, the TEE ensures CVM’s memory integrity and confidentiality, while the hTPM measures pre-boot integrity, and the cTPM covers workload and runtime components. With an untrusted hypervisor, TPM enhances security by measuring host and cloud-native elements. TEE focuses on its TCB and relies on TPM for static measurements, forming a comprehensive trusted computing environment jointly.

- **RTR: TEE & TPM Composite Attestation**

For RTR, TPM and TEE work collaboratively to provide a “dual assurance” mechanism for accurately verifying system

trustworthiness. The TEE reports the integrity of its runtime environment, while the TPM offers trust measurements during CVM launch and runtime. For more details, refer to Section IV-C.

- **RTS: TEE Relies on TPM Trusted Storage**

Currently, CVMs do not provide storage protection for application keys within the TEE. As a cryptographic coprocessor, TPM serves as a complementary technology, enabling hardware-based key storage protection for applications running in CVMs. Therefore, TPM is fully responsible for the RTS, and we propose two approaches for CVM key storage: hTPM-based and cTPM-based.

(a) hTPM-based key storage (b) cTPM-based key storage

Fig. 3: TPM storage key protection structure

The hTPM-based approach leverages the standard TPM 2.0 key hierarchy by creating a CVM Storage Root Key (SRK) under the Owner hierarchy (Figure 3a). This method maintains TPM compatibility and avoids persisting the CVM’s *MasterSecret* in NVRAM. To support secure derivation, we introduce `TPM2_CreateCVMRootKey`, which derives the CVM SRK from the *MasterSecret* and protects it under the Owner SRK. However, this approach complicates key lifecycle management, as revocation may affect the Owner hierarchy, and recovery becomes difficult without persistent *MasterSecret* storage. In contrast, the cTPM-based approach introduces a new Confidential Computing (CC) hierarchy (Figure 3b), where each CVM maintains an independent key tree rooted in a *PrimaryMasterSecret* stored in NVRAM. CVM keys are generated through the `TPM2_CreateCVMKey` interface, ensuring strong isolation between CVMs, simplifying revocation, and eliminating dependency on the Owner hierarchy. This design, however, requires extending TPM functionality and diverges from the standard TPM model.

Regardless of which type of approach is used, there are a variety of keys that can be derived for different purposes based on RTS.

B. Confidential TPM

The confidential TPM (cTPM) is designed with the principles of minimal trust, minimal dependency, and strong isolation to support a high-assurance, verifiable confidential computing environment. Unlike TEE-based vTPM schemes [20], [14], the cTPM operates as an independent TPM device CVM, delivering hardware-backed security. It ensures secure and efficient TPM usage in the cloud, maintaining protection even in the presence of a compromised hypervisor, provided the cTPM is configured correctly.

- **TPM Access**

In cTPM, the hardware TPM (hTPM) is directly passed through to a virtual machine and exposed as a virtual TPM instance. This instance does not perform actual computation or storage; instead, it forwards all TPM operations to the underlying hTPM, enabling transparent and trusted access from within the CVM. Within the User CVM, a cTPM Agent running at VMPL0 is responsible for establishing a secure communication channel between the TEE-protected CVM and the TPM device CVM hosting the physical TPM. As an extension, cTPM also includes a vTPM implemented in software to provide supplementary TPM functionalities beyond what the hTPM supports. This software vTPM interacts with external software stacks to emulate full TPM capabilities.

When using an hTPM, efficient utilization of I/O devices in the CVM is critical. As discussed in [43], CVM I/O overhead mainly consists of: (1) VM Exits, (2) bounce buffer mechanisms, and (3) network packet processing. While the third is network-specific and irrelevant for TPM, the first and second parts are crucial. VM Exits occur because the CVM lacks direct device access, requiring hypervisor intervention, leading to significant context-switch overhead. Bounce buffers are necessary because TEE enforces encrypted memory isolation, preventing untrusted host components from directly accessing CVM memory. Consequently, a shared memory buffer is utilized to mediate data transfers, which incurs additional memory copy costs.

VMExit Overhead. As noted in [43], to reduce VM Exit overhead, Posted Interrupts on new generation CPUs lower the cost significantly (by an order of magnitude compared to traditional CVMs), though still higher than standard VMs. To optimize performance, we employ a VirtIO-based zero-copy design using ring buffers and shared memory. The Virtqueue is lock-free and aligned to page boundaries to avoid performance degradation from page splits. I/O operations are triggered via event notifications to minimize VM Exits. To bypass the hypervisor and enable direct data access, a shared memory region is registered at boot using the GHCB protocol. The TPM accesses this region via DMA, avoiding hypervisor mediation. Since shared memory pages are no longer protected by memory encryption and integrity, we introduce IOMMU-based isolation to secure the DMA path. A dedicated IOMMU domain is assigned to the TPM controller, mapping only the registered shared memory pages. These mappings are hardware-enforced and cannot be altered by the hypervisor. Under SEV-SNP, memory page states are managed by the RMP hardware, ensuring that the CVM must explicitly trigger state transitions (e.g., Private \rightarrow Shared) and cannot be forged by the hypervisor.

Bounce Buffer Overhead. To eliminate the traditional overhead of bounce buffers commonly seen in I/O virtualization, we design a high-performance trusted data channel based on shared memory, enabling end-to-end encrypted communication between CVM and hTPM. Under the SEV-SNP architecture, private pages are inaccessible to devices, necessitating bounce buffers as secure intermediaries to facilitate data exchange—adding memory copy overhead and latency.

To bypass this limitation, our approach leverages encrypted shared memory, secured by page table encryption, to eliminate the need for bounce buffers. During TPM initialization, a seed for the Confidential Computing (CC) hierarchy is generated. The CVM authenticates the hTPM via the SPDm protocol and establishes a secure session key based on this seed. Using the in-kernel crypto API, the CVM performs end-to-end encryption and decryption, ensuring confidentiality and integrity even when plaintext temporarily resides in shared memory. The shared memory regions are dynamically allocated and recycled through the VirtIO driver, with each region bound to a dedicated I/O virtqueue to support parallel transmission.

By combining secure memory sharing and cryptographic channel protection, we achieve zero-copy, high-throughput data transfer under SEV-SNP without compromising security.

For vTPM, a critical concern is the secure persistence of storage. The NVRAM stores essential data, including keys, PCR values, seeds, and other sensitive information. As the core data of vTPM resides in the NVRAM, protecting its confidentiality and integrity is essential for vTPM’s overall security.

Protection of NVRAM. To ensure NVRAM confidentiality, persistent storage can be secured using an encrypted filesystem. The entire VM disk is encrypted with dm-crypt and LUKS during VM launch. QEMU is modified to support dm-crypt, enabling the creation and mounting of an encrypted filesystem at launch. For enhanced security, the dm-crypt encryption key (K_{seal}) is derived and protected by the hTPM. During VM launch, the key is unsealed from the hTPM based on launch measurements, ensuring that only the intended CVM can access and restore its vTPM state.

To maintain the integrity of NVRAM, only specific CVMs are allowed to modify the NVRAM stored in the encrypted file system. However, attacks such as physical disk replacement fall outside the scope of this solution.

Following the integration of the cTPM, a key design objective is the persistent and secure storage of cryptographic materials in NVRAM.

To ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and binding of keys, the cTPM adopts a digital envelope scheme. In this scheme, primary keys encrypt subordinate keys using symmetric encryption and authenticate them via HMAC. However, if the seed changes, previously derived third-level keys may remain valid, posing a security risk. To address this, the cTPM integrates a random manager that combines TPM hardware RNG with TEE-based entropy sources. It supports user-defined parameters and performs hierarchical seed derivation using deterministic KDFs, ensuring high entropy quality and isolation across key hierarchies. Entropy sources are selected dynamically based on the privilege level of the target key, with stronger randomness allocated to higher-trust domains. All derived keys are sealed to maintain confidentiality across reboots or migrations. During initialization, seeds for the four TPM hierarchies (CC, Endorsement, Owner, and Platform) are generated and persistently stored in NVRAM along with version numbers or timestamps. Each derived key blob in-

cludes its version metadata, allowing the system to detect seed updates and invalidate obsolete keys. This design preserves forward security and key chain consistency.

- **cTPM Initialization**

The primary objective of cTPM in a CVM is to establish an independent RoT, ensuring secure key management and storage. During the CVM launch, the cTPM established trust by associating vEK with the hTPM’s EK, which inherited the platform RoT. It obtains a certificate chain issued by the OCA, which verifies the device identity, ensures its legitimacy, and supports subsequent remote attestation. This process enables identity binding and trust inheritance. During identity binding, the sealing key (K_{Seal}) used for the persistence storage is passed to the protected environment of CVM through key injection. K_{Seal} is safeguarded by hardware-based protection, secures cTPM’s internal storage, and maintains the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive data. Even if the CVM is restarted or migrated, its security state remains intact.

- **Calling cTPM**

To enable secure access from the User CVM to the hardware TPM, we design a cTPM Agent that runs at VMPL0 within the User CVM. Acting as an intermediary to the cTPM CVM, this agent establishes a secure channel, encapsulates TPM commands, manages encrypted communication, and handles responses.

Upon CVM launch, the cTPM Agent initializes at VMPL0, loads local configurations, verifies hardware support for SEV-SNP and VMPL, and sets up the cryptographic context and network interface. It then initiates a mutual authentication protocol with the cTPM CVM using SPD, involving certificate exchange and challenge-response. Subsequently, a session key is derived from a pre-injected CC Seed to secure the communication channel. Unlike traditional shared-memory mechanisms, the cTPM Agent uses a secure network-based channel to transmit TPM commands. It listens for TPM2_* requests from TEE applications or user-space services, encrypts the payload with a MAC and session context, and forwards it to the cTPM CVM. Responses are decrypted and verified before being returned to the caller, ensuring compatibility with standard TPM interfaces.

- **Application of cTPM**

In practice, CVM trusted access to peripherals also relies on collaboration between the TEE and TPM. For example, the TDISP [44] extends the TPM’s NV Index to bind I/O path measurement information to the server platform, ensuring the integrity and origin authenticity. Typically, the TEE measures runtime I/O path properties, while the TPM stores results and generates attestation reports for CVM-level verification.

This approach extends to high-performance devices like GPUs, where cTPM enhances standard TPM capabilities with fine-grained, dynamic I/O attestation via TEE integration. Upon CVM launch, the TEE and cTPM jointly measure attributes such as device BDF, driver versions, firmware hashes, IOMMU mappings and AI module measurements. These values are extended into dedicated PCRs and associated

with device-specific identifiers. During attestation, the TPM extends PCRs with GPU state and signs the resulting values to ensure integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation. The CVM then verifies the composite report by checking its content and digital signature. If successful, the CVM can securely use the GPU for computation.

C. Composite Attestation

To unify multiple RoTs, we have developed a collaborative attestation framework combining TEE and TPM. This framework provides unified attestation and verification through a trusted attestation token and securely protected platform secret information. It addresses the challenge of unified attestation across heterogeneous TEE platforms, TPM nodes, and composite nodes (e.g., SEV+TPM), enabling secure data sharing and trust establishment in large-scale confidential computing clusters.

To mitigate the security risks and performance overhead of separate TEE and TPM attestations in CVM platforms, we propose a composite attestation protocol that enables efficient and trustworthy cooperation between both trust roots. In conventional designs, TEE and TPM generate independent attestation reports, which the agent later aggregates. This disjointed process introduces attack surfaces, such as forged CVM identities and report splicing, where reports from different platforms or VMs are maliciously combined to deceive verifiers. Moreover, dual-path attestation incurs considerable overhead—requiring multiple user-kernel transitions, hardware interactions, signature operations, and report transmissions—leading to increased latency and system load. In contrast, our composite attestation protocol synthesizes TEE and TPM measurements into a single report via a unified agent and coordinated kernel-level integration. This design not only reduces attestation latency but also enforces end-to-end integrity, effectively preventing splicing attacks. In general, its implementation poses several challenges:

Verification gap: Verifier lacks mechanisms to confirm that the TEE report and TPM quote originate from the same physical platform or CVM, breaking cross-root trust continuity.

Lack of binding: Existing structures (e.g., TD_REPORT, ATTESTATION_REPORT, TPM Quote) lack architectural-level cryptographic binding, allowing adversaries to construct forged attestations from mismatched components.

Replay risk: Exploit an outdated TEE report with a CVM instance that is not connected to a genuine TPM, forging a seemingly valid composite attestation to mislead the relying party and potentially exfiltrate sensitive data.

Delayed measurement attacks: Although TPM PCR is immutable, it is not strictly time-bound. Attackers can defer or manipulate events, committing them post-recovery to misrepresent the system state.

A robust composite attestation protocol combines TEE and TPM to establish a unified trust system that integrates static and dynamic trust chains (Figure 4). It employs joint signatures and timestamping to ensure coherence, prevent reuse, and defend against composition and forgery attacks, with minimal

performance overhead. The protocol operates in two phases: *Initialization* and *Attestation*.

(1) Initialization phase

Take SEV-SNP as an example, during TEE initialization, a unique $VCEK$ is derived from the ASP and microcode version, signed by the ASK and the AMD ARK, forming the certificate chain’s root. The OCA verifies the certificate chain and generates the $Cert_{VCEK}$ and $MasterSecret$, which are securely sent to the TEE.

Similarly, during TPM initialization, the seed key (EPSeed) is generated and used by the TPM_Manufacture(EPSeed) to initialize the EK. EK is then used to securely generate the AIK. The $RegistrarAIK$ function interacts with the OCA to verify the authenticity of EK and AIK via $ActivateCredential$, ultimately obtaining the AIK certificate ($Cert_{AIK}$), which, along with the AIK public key (AIK_{pub}), is sent to the verifier for authenticity verification.

(2) Attestation phase

Attestation supports two protocols. Attestation-TEE-TPM demonstrates the process of embedding the TEE Report into the TPM Quote, while Attestation-TPM-TEE illustrates the process of embedding the TPM Quote into the TEE Report. Taking the Attestation-TEE-TPM process as an example, Attestation-TPM-TEE is similar.

1. The verifier (Attestation Service, AS) initiates the attestation process by sending an $AttestationRequest$ to the TPM, which may include PCR values to specify the system components’ state to be attested.

2. The TPM sends a $GuestReportRequest$ to the TEE, which then generates a measured report, TEE_Report , signed using $VCEK$. To prevent splicing attacks, the $keyboot$ derived during the initialization negotiation is used to produce an authenticated encrypted report, $aeTEE_Report$, which is then sent to the TPM.

3. To enhance temporal consistency and replay resistance during runtime PCR extension, a Secure TSC is introduced as a trusted time source. The current TSC value is combined with the hash value of the workload to be extended as input to a hash function, and the result is extended into the target PCR as follows:

$$PCR_i = \text{Hash}(PCR_{old} || \text{Hash}(\text{workload}) || \text{Secure_TSC}) \quad (1)$$

4. The TPM decrypts $aeTEE_Report$ using $keyboot$ to obtain the original $deTEE_Report$. It then executes TPM_Quote to attest to the current runtime environment in the PCR, including the TPM state and platform configuration. Unlike the original measurement, the $Total_Report$ is generated, incorporating the $deTEE_Report$ for a comprehensive view of both TPM and TEE states.

5. The verifier receives and validates the $Total_Report$, verifying the integrity of the TPM_Quote and confirming the authenticity of the TEE_Report . Once validated, the AS generates an attestation token confirming the trustworthiness of the environment.

Upon successful attestation, the AS issues a unified JWT format token comprising a header, payload, and signature.

The $token_header$ includes metadata such as validity period, certificate references, and format version to prevent replay of expired tokens. The $token_payload$ embeds a composite attestation report, combining TEE and TPM results with key platform data. The $token_signature$, generated by the AS, ensures integrity and enables verification by trusted parties. This structure binds attestation evidence with contextual information (e.g., timestamps and attestation types), mitigating forgery and concatenation risks in composite attestation. For detailed token contents, see Appendix A.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Our implementation builds on AMD’s SEV-SNP software stack (QEMU, OVMF, Linux), with modifications to the host/guest kernel and Microsoft’s TPM stack to support composite attestation and cTPM.

A. cTPM-CVM Initialization

As shown in the Figure 5, the SEV-SNP launch process is integrated to complete the initialization of cTPM. The hypervisor initiates the $LAUNCH_START$ command, which initializes the SEV platform and assigns a new memory encryption key (VEK) to the cTPM (1). The hTPM initializes by generating an Endorsement Key (EK), deriving a hardware-derived key (hDK) for communication based on the CC seed, and assigning a unique identifier (ID) to the cTPM. The EK public key (EK_{pub}), hDK public key (hDK_{pub}), and ID are then securely transmitted to the hypervisor as a secret value (2). Next, the $LAUNCH_UPDATE_DATA$ command instructs the PSP to measure the guest memory region, incorporating EK_{pub} , hDK_{pub} , and ID into the SEV-SNP launch measurement. This data is stored in a normal page and encrypted using the VEK , preventing privilege-level attacks or eavesdropping (3). The $LAUNCH_FINISH$ command finalizes the CVM launch and activates the cTPM platform (4), but the initialization process is incomplete.

Upon launch, the cTPM integrates its initial state into the RoT, ensuring integrity for future key management and remote attestation (5). The cTPM then requests an attestation report from the PSP (6) to verify that it is operating in a protected confidential computing environment. After successful verification, it extracts the measurement from the report (7). The cTPM generates its own confidential Endorsement key (cEK), and the cDK for communication, and encrypts its public key (cEK_{pub} , cDK_{pub}), the assigned ID, and the randomly generated temporary key K_c using the hTPM’s EK_{pub} . This forms the encrypted payload $Enc_{EK}(cEK_{pub}, cDK_{pub}, ID, K_c)$, which is transmitted to the hTPM along with $H(\text{measurement})$. Meanwhile, the cTPM uses cDK_{priv} and hDK_{pub} to calculate the $chTCK$ for communication with the hTPM. The hTPM decrypts the data using its private EK (EK_{priv}), validates the ID to authenticate the cTPM. Upon successful verification, signs cEK_{pub} with its EK_{priv} to generate $Cert_{EK}(cEK)$. The certificate is then forwarded to the OCA for signing, producing the complete certificate chain $Cert_{OCA}(Cert_{EK}(cEK))$. Similarly, hTPM

Fig. 4: Composite Attestation Protocol Based on TEE and TPM

Fig. 5: Trust Binding in cTPM Initialization

Fig. 6: A Trusted Channel between TEE and TPM

uses the same algorithm to calculate the $chTCK$ used to communicate with the cTPM using hDK_{priv} and cDK_{pub} (9). To secure internal storage, the hTPM derives a sealing key (K_{seal}) from measurements to protect cTPM data. It returns the $Cert_{OCA}(Cert_{EK}(cEK))$ and $Enc_{K_c}(ID||K_{seal})$, encrypted with HMAC-SHA384 (10). The cTPM extracts the certificates for attestation and decrypts K_{seal} to encrypt its NVRAM, ensuring data remains protected across reboots or migrations. In subsequent communications, the cTPM and hTPM use $chTCK$ to transmit data transparently.

B. Composite Attestation

To support composite attestation and defend against report splicing and forgery attacks, we design a secure trusted channel between the TEE firmware and TPM. During the CVM launch, the TEE and TPM negotiate a communication key, and the attestation reports are transmitted using authenticated encryption to ensure confidentiality and integrity. This channel also enables secure key provisioning by the cTPM, as shown in Figure 6.

The process begins with key pair generation and mutual authentication. The TEE firmware generates an ephemeral key pair $\{PDH_{pub}, PDH_{priv}\}$ and constructs an authentication certificate (PDH_{Cert}) containing its public key (PDH_{pub}), TEE ID (TEE_{ID}), and signature (TEE_{Sign}). PDH_{Cert} is then sent to the TPM for verification. Similarly, the TPM

generates its own key pair $\{TDH_{pub}, TDH_{priv}\}$ and creates an authentication certificate (TDH_{Cert}) with its public key (TDH_{pub}), TPM ID (TPM_{ID}), and signature (TPM_{Sign}). During the LAUNCH_START, the TPM securely writes its TDH_{Cert} into a secret page, allowing the TEE firmware to retrieve it. Once both parties have exchanged public keys, they compute a shared secret (S) using Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH). The TEE derives the S_{TEE} by computing $ECDH(PDH_{priv}, TDH_{pub})$, while the TPM uses the same method to calculate S_{TPM} , ensuring both arrive at the same secret value. This shared secret is then used to derive cryptographic keys for secure communication.

This ensures that only the TEE firmware and TPM can derive the communication keys. A Key Derivation Function (KDF) is then applied to the S to generate an authentication key, where $keyboot = KDF(S, "AEAD")$. With this trusted channel established, TEE and TPM securely exchange remote attestation reports to ensure the integrity of the composite attestation. During composite attestation, when requesting a report from peers (4), the original report is encrypted using AES-GCM with $keyboot$ and an associated identifier to prevent tampering and ensure authentication (5).

Upon receipt, both parties decrypt the reports and verify their authenticity and integrity. Once validated, the attestation reports are aggregated into a unified attestation, which is then securely transmitted to the remote verifier for final validation.

Fig. 7: Composite Attestation Interface Design

To implement the composite attestation protocol, we need to modify the relevant structures of the TPM and TEE.

As shown on the left of Figure 7, we extend the standard TPMS_QUOTE_INFO structure to TPMS_CCQUOTE_INFO and introduce a new command, TPM2_CCQuote, based on TPM2_Quote. The extension adds a teeReport field of type TPM2B_TEE_REPORT, a variable-length array up to MAX_TEE_REPORT_SIZE. If the size is set to zero, the quote excludes the TEE report. The TPM2_CCQuote command enables composite attestation by accepting a TEE attestation report as UserData (TPM2B_DATA) and returning a combined attestation result.

$$\text{Total_Report} = \text{TPM2_CCQuote}_{\text{AIK}}(\text{PCR}, n, \text{TEE_Report}) \quad (2)$$

To support embedding TPM quotes into TEE reports, the TEE must implement corresponding support. In AMD SEV-SNP, the Reserved section of the TEE report is reused to carry the TPM quote, aligned to a 64-byte boundary for performance. The TPM data is hashed and incorporated into the TEE measurement, producing a composite report that includes both the VM state and TPM measurements, as illustrated on the right of Figure 7.

$$\text{Total_Report} = \text{TEE_Report}_{\text{VCEK}}(\text{Att_info}, n, \text{TPM_Quote}) \quad (3)$$

C. Confidential AI based on CCxTrust

Based on the CCxTrust, we build a Confidential AI Inference System that integrates CVMs (e.g., SEV-SNP), confidential GPUs, and cTPM to provide end-to-end protection across the AI inference pipeline, including prompt input, model execution, and sensitive data handling.

The system includes a user-side CVM (TEEUser) that initiates inference requests and a cloud-side CVM (TEEServer), which operates as a composite node equipped with a confidential GPU and cTPM. TEEServer provides LLM inference services (e.g., GLM-4, DeepSeek). A trusted channel is established via mutual attestation to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of all exchanged data.

During initialization, TEEUser and TEEServer register with the OCA to obtain a *Node_cert* and a *MasterSecret*, then submit composite attestation reports to the AS. TEEServer additionally verifies model file integrity using its TEE and cTPM. After successful verification, the AS issues a token, enabling both parties to establish mutual trust.

In the inference phase, TEEUser and TEEServer authenticate using the token and derive a session key from the *MasterSecret* to establish a secure channel. Prompts are encrypted and processed within TEEServer, and results are securely returned without exposure to the cloud platform.

By leveraging CCxTrust, this system ensures robust runtime protection against model theft, prompt injection, data leakage, and environment tampering, delivering end-to-end confidentiality for LLM inference workloads. The code of the composite node can be found in the GitHub repository ¹.

VI. SECURITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we will analyze the security of CCxTrust. It does not consider side channel attacks against the platform. Based on the threat model, attacker behavior is classified into four categories.

(1) **Physical attacks on the bus** The CVM employs hardware memory encryption managed by a dedicated security processor, preventing unauthorized access even in the presence of physical bus snooping. During the boot process, the hTPM generates the CC hierarchy seed while establishing a mutually authenticated secure channel to prevent tampering and replay attacks. Shared memory is protected by IOMMU isolation and RMP-supported integrity protection. These mechanisms collectively ensure that CCxTrust prevents secret leakage even under bus-level tampering or man-in-the-middle attacks.

(2) **Privilege-level attacks** To mitigate threats posed by attackers with hypervisor privileges, CCxTrust employs a three-stage measurement to block backdoors and detect rollback. The cTPM securely seals encryption keys, ensuring that tampered or replaced images cannot unseal sensitive data. Secure channels between cTPM and hTPM, encrypted storage, and strict CVM-host isolation prevent privilege escalation and unauthorized access. By integrating robust key management, attestation, and isolation, CCxTrust ensures the integrity and confidentiality of critical data under privileged attacks.

(3) **Workload-based attacks** Attackers may exploit software vulnerabilities within a CVM to control workloads or target the guest kernel, potentially accessing cTPM data. The third-stage measurement detects anomalies in guest kernels or workloads, triggering isolation or key resets to prevent data leakage. The cTPM’s layered key management ensures compromised workloads cannot access root or cross-CVM keys, maintaining security boundaries and preventing key propagation. Through the composite attestation and isolated key management, CCxTrust ensures that attackers cannot compromise CVM security or propagate key leaks across layers.

(4) **Attacks on the composite attestation protocol** Composite attestation integrates TEE and TPM RoTs to establish hardware-level integrity and authenticity, mitigating threats such as CVM impersonation and report splicing. Certification chains of VCEK and AIK, validated by the Owner CA, ensure RoT uniqueness and trust. The attestation report includes joint measurements from both TEE and TPM, preventing forgery

¹https://anonymous.4open.science/r/compositd_node-D4DA

and substitution by binding data from both components and adding timestamps. The attestation token is signed by the service, embeds validity, certificates, and hardware details to prevent reuse. Together, these mechanisms safeguard attestation integrity in confidential computing environments.

To address potential protocol vulnerabilities, we systematically validate the security of CCxTrust through the Protocol Composition Logic (PCL) [45]. The formal modeling methodology and theorem-proving workflows are thoroughly explicated in Appendix B.

1) Protocol modeling

Within the overall scheme, there exist four participating entities, namely Owner CA, TEE, TPM, and Verifier, denoted as \hat{C} , \hat{E} , \hat{P} , and \hat{V} respectively.

2) Invariants and security properties

- Protocol invariants

The following introduces the invariants relied upon during the protocol analysis process, all of which are derived from attestation routines and security assumptions, specifically as follows:

$$\Gamma_1 \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Decrypt}(X, \text{ENC}_K(m)) \supset \text{Has}(\hat{X}, K^{-1}) \quad (4)$$

$$\Gamma_2 \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{K_X^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) \supset \text{Receive}(X, \text{request}) > \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{K_X^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) \quad (5)$$

$$\Gamma_3 \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{X}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Verify}(V, \text{SIG}_{K_X^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}) \wedge (\text{Send}(V, \text{msg}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{msg}, \text{token}))) \quad (6)$$

- Protocol security properties

Theorem 1 Correctness of certificate issuance.

$$\phi_{C, \text{init}} \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{X}, \text{cert}_C) \supset \text{Has}(\hat{X}, K_{AK}^{-1}) \wedge \text{Send}(\hat{C}, \text{msg}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{msg}, \text{cert}) \quad (7)$$

Theorem 2: Correctness of attestation.

$$\phi_{C, \text{attest}} \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{X}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Has}(\hat{X}, K_{XV}) \wedge \text{Send}(\hat{V}, m) \wedge \text{Contains}(m, \text{token}) \quad (8)$$

Theorem 3: Integrity of attestation report.

$$\phi_{I, \text{attest}} \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{K_X^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{X}, \text{token}) \supset (\text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{X}, \text{request}) > \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{AK^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) \wedge \text{Sign}(V, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{token}))) \quad (9)$$

Theorem 4 Authentication of attestation report.

$$\phi_{A, \text{attest}} \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge (\text{Receive}(X, \hat{X}, \hat{V}, \text{request}) > \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{K_{AK}^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}))) \supset (\text{FirstSend}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{X}, \text{request}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{request}, n) \wedge (\text{Verify}(V, \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{K_{AK}^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}))) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{totalReport}, n))) \quad (10)$$

Theorem 1 proves the correctness of identity certificate issuance, ensuring the authoritative origin of certificate generation. **Theorem 2** validates the correctness of attestation routines by demonstrating their compliance with the protocol's formal specifications and security objectives. **Theorem 3** guarantees the integrity of attestation reports through an analysis of their generation and verification processes. **Theorem 4** confirms the authentication of attestation reports via signature

and identity certificate mechanisms, ensuring the authenticity of their origin.

3) Protocol composition

The Initialization and Attestation protocols satisfy the sequential composition rule of PCL. By applying PCL's sequential composition rule S1, it can be formally demonstrated that the two sub-protocols collectively satisfy the set of security invariants for both protocols, formally:

$$\Gamma_1 \cup \Gamma_2 \vdash \phi_{C, \text{init}} \text{ and } \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \phi_{C, \text{attest}}$$

Theorem 5 Correctness of the Confidential Computing Composite Attestation Protocol.

$$\phi_{C, \text{CCxTrust}} \equiv \text{Honest}(\hat{X}) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{X}, \text{token}) \supset (\text{Has}(\hat{X}, K_{AK}) \wedge \text{Sign}(X, \text{SIG}_{K_{AK}^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}))) \wedge (\text{Send}(C, \hat{C}, \hat{X}, m) \wedge \text{Contains}(m, K_{AK})) > \text{Verify}(V, \text{SIG}_{K_{AK}^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) > \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{X}, m) \wedge \text{Contains}(m, \text{token}) \quad (11)$$

We formally verified the TEE and TPM composite attestation protocol using a process-based verification model and the ProVerif automated analysis tool. The analysis confirms the protocol's authenticity, as well as the confidentiality and integrity of its communication. Verification details and source code are available on GitHub². For a full description of the verification process, see Appendix C.

VII. EVALUATION

In this section, we focus on the main overheads of CCxTrust from different aspects. Our experimental setup consists of an SNP-enabled server, a TPM chip, and a Mobile Workstation. The SNP server is equipped with an AMD EPYC 7763 64-core processor, 128GB of memory, and 4TB of disk storage. The host kernel uses version 6.12.0-rc4-snp-host-5a170ce1a082, while the guest kernel is the same as the host kernel. The TPM 2.0 chip used is the Nation Technology Z32H330TC. The mobile workstation uses an Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9980HK 2.40GHz processor, 32GB of memory, and a 2TB hard disk, with the host kernel being version 5.15.0-105-generic.

Overall, CCxTrust introduces minimal performance overhead across CVM operations, remote attestation, and confidential AI applications. It significantly enhances the security and resilience of the confidential computing platform, making it practical and effective for real-world deployment.

A. Confidential VM Performance

Measurement and Monitoring. We evaluated the measurement time overhead on SPEC CPU 2017. The CVM was configured with 32 vCPUs and 32GB of memory. We selected 10 benchmarks from the Intspeed suite for testing. The results (Figure 8a) showed that the performance loss of using the CVM was about 10% compared to ordinary VMs. When dynamic integrity monitoring was performed in CVM, the performance loss increased by less than 1.5% based on TEE & TPM.

²<https://anonymous.4open.science/r/Proverif-2EB6>

(a) SPEC CPU 2017 intspeed

(b) TPM performance in different Types

(c) EFS performance in CVM

Fig. 8: Confidential VM performance

cTPM CVM. To support the RTS, we extended the cTPM with a CC hierarchy through minimal code changes. Table II compares the added boot module’s LoC. The TPM_Manufacture function adds 0.011 ms to boot time, about 8% overhead. Performance tests (Figure 8b) show AIK generation and import are the most time-consuming operations, while signing, quoting, verification, and unsealing perform acceptably. The software TPM simulator outperforms hardware TPMs due to the lack of hardware and communication delays. Among hardware TPMs, PCIe chips outperform USB devices due to higher bandwidth and lower latency. CVMs incur a 10–20% performance loss from memory encryption overhead. Overall, cTPM incurs a 16.47% overhead compared to software TPMs but delivers stronger hardware-backed security, maintaining acceptable performance.

Storage. We implemented an encrypted file system for NVRAM and evaluated performance with 100 file read/write operations, using a normal CVM as baseline. As shown in Figure 8c, small data (10k, 100k) incurred minimal write overhead, while large files (e.g., 1GB) saw increased costs from key management and encryption. Read performance dropped 30% for small files but improved for larger data due to key caching. For data beyond 1GB, I/O bandwidth became the main bottleneck. Performance remained optimal for typical NVRAM sizes (<100MB).

TABLE II: Modified modules in TPM (LoC)

Module	Original	New	Modify	Ratio
CryptInit	49	0	0	-
NvManufacture	392	20	28	7.1%
CryptStartup	10	0	0	-
PCRManufacture	33	8	13	39.4%
HierarchyInit	57	20	22	38.6%
Total	541	48	63	11.6%

B. Attestation Performance

We evaluated the overhead of establishing a trusted channel based on SEV. As shown in Table III, the total latency increases by 3.07% compared to normal CVM launch, with most of the overhead incurred during the LAUNCH_UPDATE phase due to additional memory page measurement and encryption. Although 58.2% of the LAUNCH_START time is spent on ECDH (increasing the LAUNCH_START time by 139.3% compared to the original), its cost is negligible in the overall launch time. For post-launch encrypted data transmission, the transfer time grows linearly with file size. For reports smaller than 2 KB, AES-GCM achieves a throughput of 39.85 MBps.

TABLE III: A trusted communication channel launch latency (us)

(a) SEV-side Channel			(b) TPM-side Channel		
Phase	Original	Ours	Overhead	Phase	Ours
START	2553	6108	139.3%	Verifysignature	487.6
UPDATE	613986	629497	2.5%	CreatePrimary	640.8
FINISH	32745	33628	2.7%	EcdhZGen	299.2
Lifespan	-	41939	-	Lifespan	1535.1

We establish a baseline for the attestation operation performance using AMD SEV-SNP and cTPM. We compare it with the attestation time of the composite protocol, as shown in the Figure 9a. The results show that compositing the TEE report into the TPM report (TPM(TEE)) is 20.3% faster than the total time for independent attestations. On the other hand, combining the TPM report into the TEE report (TEE(TPM)) is 57.2% faster than the total time for independent attestations. The main reason for this is the reduction in interactions with the upper software stack. As expected, the composite attestation is much more efficient than the independent attestations of TEE and TPM.

To evaluate concurrency in attestation, results in Figure 9b show the attestation server supports over 10,000 concurrent requests in confidential computing clusters, with per-request latency under 1.2 s, token generation below 100 microseconds, and average verification under 0.3 ms. Figure 9c reveals that SEV node attestation report verification takes about 1 ms, longer than TPM’s 300 μ s. However, TPM’s overall concurrent attestation time is an order of magnitude higher than SEV’s due to hardware constraints—the TPM relies on a physical chip for evidence generation, whereas SEV leverages the CPU. Despite these differences, both remain within acceptable performance bounds. As cluster size scales, the attestation server maintains stable performance, effectively supporting large-scale concurrent attestations.

C. Confidential AI Applications

We implemented a confidential AI inference system based on CCxTrust to evaluate secure inference performance. CCxTrust integrates TEE, cTPM, and GPU through a composite attestation mechanism, ensuring the confidentiality of prompts, data, and the TEE itself. Using an AMD SEV-SNP CVM and an NVIDIA A6000 GPU, we deployed the ChatGLM3-6B model and established a secure channel for prompt delivery and inference execution. The attestation report (Appendix A) combines CVM launch measurements with model measure-

Fig. 9: CCxTrust attestation performance: In Figure a, "TEE+TPM" denotes separate reports, "TPM(TEE)" and "TEE(TPM)" indicate composite reports. In Figure b, "Con_att time" is the total attestation duration, including challenge and response; "Att_time" is the AS processing time; "Token_time" is the time to issue the token. In Figure c, "TPM_*" and "SEV_*" indicate nodes led by TPM and SEV, respectively.

Fig. 10: Confidential AI Inference Performance

ments (e.g., ChatGLM3-6B), providing end-to-end guarantees of model integrity and execution environment trustworthiness. The measurement throughput of TEE and TPM exceeds 250 MB/s, and the measurement time scales linearly with model size. Disk read speed and model file fragmentation have a direct impact on performance. During attestation, SEV-SNP CVM attestation takes approximately 150 ms. In comparison, the cTPM-based composite attestation with the addition of model files and GPU environment increases the total to about 980 ms ($\approx 6.48\times$), primarily due to the large model size and higher TPM attestation overhead. Performance evaluated with 10 different prompts shows an average overhead of 6% compared to native inference (Figure 10), with slight variations due to inherent per-prompt execution differences. These results demonstrate that CCxTrust effectively preserves data confidentiality and model integrity with minimal performance impact, making it suitable for high-assurance AI deployments.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

Secure Virtualization Systems. Numerous research efforts and commercial products have been proposed to build secure virtualization systems. For instance, AMD SEV [2], Intel TDX [1], and ARM CCA [3] introduce the abstraction of CVMs through hardware extensions, playing a critical role in memory encryption and integrity protection. The design of CCxTrust exhibits broad applicability across platforms (as shown in Table IV). However, since CCA is designed for the ARM architecture, it faces compatibility challenges compared to x86-based SEV and TDX. Some features must be replaced with composite mechanisms. For example, ARM CCA lacks VMPL-style instruction-level isolation but can

achieve equivalent or similar isolation through combinations such as using PIE [46].

TABLE IV: CCxTrust cross-CVM features

Plat.	cTPM			Com Attestation Get Report
	Mem.	Intg.	Agent	
SEV	GHCB	RMP	VMPL	SNP_GUEST_REQUEST
TDX	GHCI	PAMT	TD-part.	TDG.MR.REPORT
CCA	RHI	GPT	PIE [46]	RSL_ATTESTATION_TOKEN_*

Confidential TPM. To extend trust to devices and eliminate rebound buffer overhead, academia and industry are advancing the direct allocation of devices to the CVM via TDISP [44]. Intel [47] and AMD [48] have proposed trusted I/O solutions that can be adapted in the future to support cTPM.

Remote attestation. SVSM enables remote attestation by combining TEE and a temporary vTPM, removing the cloud provider from the trust domain [14]. However, it relies on a single RoT and stepwise verification, making it vulnerable to splicing attacks. In contrast, our composite attestation integrates TEE and TPM into a unified RoT, enhancing trust and eliminating such risks. Unlike SVSM-vTPM's vendor-bound model, our system supports a user-controlled trust model, decoupling trust from cloud providers in multi-tenant environments. While SVSM uses a temporary vTPM with no persistent storage, our cTPM is securely bound to the hTPM, enabling persistent storage and ensuring full lifecycle protection of keys and states.

IX. CONCLUSION

To address data security and trust gaps in cloud environments, this paper proposes CCxTrust, a confidential computing platform built on a collaborative RoT combining TEE and TPM. CCxTrust enables parallel independent RTM, composited RTR, and TPM-based RTS, supporting mutual authentication, trusted channel establishment, and secure key provisioning. By integrating cTPM and an efficient composite attestation protocol, CCxTrust enhances both security and attestation performance. A prototype on AMD SEV-SNP demonstrates strong security guarantees with low overhead, supporting secure data sharing and multi-party collaboration in confidential AI scenarios. While our work is specific to AMD, the approach is adaptable to other CVM architectures.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This research does not involve human subjects, personal data, or potentially harmful activities, and we believe it does not pose any ethical concerns.

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APPENDIX

A. Implementation of composite attestation

The composite attestation report generated by the composite node integrates security measurements and signatures based on TEE and TPM, providing comprehensive trust assurance for the runtime environment and its key components. As shown in the list 1, *snp* reflects the attestation structure generated by AMD SEV-SNP, where the *snp.measurement* field records the CVM *sig_** field contains the signature from the AMD security platform to prove the authenticity and defects of the CVM measurement value. *tpm* contains the reference signature of the TPM and the *file-hash.total_hash* field represents the encrypted hash value of the LLM model (such as ChatGLM3-6B) data loaded into the CVM. This value ensures model integrity and can interrupt the PCR of the TPM. The TPM then signs the composite evidence containing the SNP report to form a unified attestation. This enables application-layer workloads to be bound to platform states and supports trusted reasoning through multi-dimensional attestations.

```

1 {
2   "snp":{
3     "version":2,
4     "guest_svn":0,
5     "guest_policy":720896,
6     "family_id":"000...000",
7     "image_id":"000...000",
8     "vmp1":1,
9     "sig_algo":1,
10    "microcode":213,
11    "snp":10,
12    "tee":0,
13    "boot_loader":3,
14    "tsme_enabled":1,
15    "smt_enabled":0,
16    "report_data":"dc5...583",
17    "measurement":"elc...f10",
18    "host_data":"000...000",
19    "id_key_digest":"000...000",
20    "author_key_digest":"000...000",

```

```

21    "report_id":"53e...959",
22    "report_id_mig_agent":"ff...fff",
23    "chip_id":"358...7dd",
24    "current_build":5,
25    "current_minor":1,
26    "current_major":53,
27    "committed_build":5,
28    "committed_minor":1,
29    "committed_major":53,
30    "sig_r":"8b8.....acf",
31    "sig_s":"490.....f3d"
32  }, "tpm":{
33    "tpm_evidence":{
34      "tpm_message":"ZmY...ZWQ=",
35      "tpm_signature":"MDA...jcy",
36      "tpm_pcrs":"MDE.....wMA=="
37    },
38    "file-hash":{
39      "measurement":[{
40        "hash":"d82...cfb",
41        "name":"/usr/local/cuda/
42          version.json",
43        "size":"2.87K", "type":"config
44          _file"
45      }],
46      "time-stamp":"2025.04.01-04:09:38",
47      "total_hash":"d93...d77"
48    }

```

Listing 1: TEE&cTPM&GPU composite attestation results

After successful attestation, the AS issues a JWT token for subsequent secure and authenticated communication between nodes. As shown in List 2, the token encapsulates essential metadata, including the attestation type, compliance status, policy hash, and runtime environment details. It also includes platform-specific measurements from SEV-SNP and TPM. The token is signed by the AS using ECC-P256 to guarantee authenticity and integrity during verification.

```

1 {
2   "token_header": {
3     "alg": "ECC-P256",
4     "type": "JWT",
5     "x5u": "<The_URL_of_certificate>"
6   },
7   "token_payload": {
8     "exp": 1649970020,
9     "iat": 1649941220,
10    "iss": "<XXX>",
11    "jti": "b65...4d5",
12    "attestation-type": "com_node:
13      sevsnpvm+tpm",
14    "compliance-status": "CCPSec",
15    "policy-hash": "<Hash_of_the_policy>"
16  },
17  "runtime": {
18    "keys": "<Key_status>",
19    "vm-configuration": "<
20      Configuration_of_vm>",
21    "report": {
22      "reportdata": "<
23        Hash_of_report>",
24      "reportid": "<ID_of_report>"

```

```

25         "pub_key": "<
                The_public_key_of_the_AK>
                "
26     },
27 },
28 "sevsnp": {
29     "sevsnpvm-bootloader-svn": 0,
30     "sevsnpvm-guestsvn": 1,
31     "sevsnpvm-imageId": "<ID_of_image
                >",
32     "sevsnpvm-is-debuggable": false,
33     "sevsnpvm-launchmeasurement": "<
                Launch_measurement>",
34     "sevsnpvm-microcode-svn": 40,
35     "sevsnpvm-snpfw-svn": 0,
36     "sevsnpvm-tee-svn": 0,
37     "sevsnpvm-vmpl": 0,
38     "version": "1.0"
39 },
40 "tpm": {
41     "tpm_version": 2,
42     "tpm_id": 2,
43     "tpm_sequence": 000,
44     "tpm_manufacturer": "<>"
45 },
46 },
47 "token_signature": {
48     "sign": "7e9...4a1"
49 }
50 }

```

Listing 2: Composite Attestation Token

B. PCL analysis

Appendix B Supplementary Content for the Formal Analysis of the Confidential Computing Composite Attestation Protocol Based on PCL. The overall analysis process is detailed in the security analysis in the main text. Throughout the protocol, we assume that each participating entity has completed key negotiation pairwise, thereby obtaining a secure channel based on symmetric encryption.

In the Initialization phase, with the initialization operation of the TEE as the starting point of the protocol, the four participating entities in the Initialization phase are modeled one by one according to the protocol. Based on the PCL system, the modeling of the Initialization phase is as follows:

```

Verifierinit ≡ (KCV, KPV) [
    receive  $\hat{C}, \hat{V}, certTEEInfo$ ;
    certVCEK, VCEKpub := symdec certTEEInfo,
        KCV;
    verify certVCEK, VCEKpub;

    receive  $\hat{P}, \hat{V}, keyCertInfo$ ;
    AIKpub, certAIK := symdec keyCertInfo, KPV;
    verify certAIK, AIKpub;
]V(VCEKpub, certVCEK, AIKpub, certAIK)

```

```

TPMinit ≡ ( $\hat{C}, \hat{V}, K_{PC}, K_{PV}, cert_{EK}$ ) [
    new EPSeed;
    new EK, AIK;
    keyInfo := symenc (AIKpub, EKpub, certEK
        ), KPC;
    send  $\hat{P}, \hat{C}, keyInfo$ ;

    receive  $\hat{C}, \hat{P}, challenge$ ;
    n' := symdec challenge, KPC;
    nonceInfo := symenc n', KPC;
    send  $\hat{P}, \hat{C}, nonceInfo$ ;
    receive  $\hat{C}, \hat{P}, certAIKInfo$ ;
    certAIK := symdec certAIKInfo, KPC;
    keyCertInfo := symenc (AIKpub, certAIK),
        KPV;
    send  $\hat{P}, \hat{V}, keyCertInfo$ ;
]P(EK, AIK, certAIK)

```

```

Owner CAinit ≡ ( $\hat{E}, \hat{P}, \hat{V}, K_{EC}, K_{PC}, K_{CV}, OCA$ ) [
    receive VCEKInfo;
    VCEKpub := symdec VCEKInfo, KEC;
    certVCEK := sign VCEKpub, OCA;
    certVCEKInfo := symenc certVCEK, KEC;
    send  $\hat{C}, \hat{E}, certVCEKInfo$ ;
    certTEEInfo := symenc (certVCEK, VCEKpub),
        KCV;
    send  $\hat{C}, \hat{V}, certTEEInfo$ ;

    receive  $\hat{P}, \hat{C}, keyInfo$ ;
    AIKpub, EKpub, certEK := symdec keyInfo, KPC;
    new n;
    challenge := symenc (n, hash(AIKpub), EKpub
        ), KPC;
    send  $\hat{C}, \hat{P}, challenge$ ;

    receive  $\hat{P}, \hat{C}, nonceInfo$ ;
    n' := symdec nonceInfo, KPC;
    match n/n';
    certAIK := sign AIKpub, OCA;
    certAIKInfo := symenc certAIK, KPC;
    send  $\hat{C}, \hat{P}, certAIKInfo$ ;
]C()

```

```

TEEinit ≡ ( $\hat{C}, K_{EC}$ ) [
    new VCEK;
    VCEKInfo := symenc VCEKpub, KEC;
    send  $\hat{E}, \hat{C}, VCEKInfo$ ;

    receive  $\hat{C}, \hat{E}, certVCEKInfo$ ;
    certVCEK := symdec certVCEKInfo, KEC;
]E(VCEK, certVCEK)

```

The Attestation phase is divided into two options according to the aggregation method of the *totalReport*. Therefore, we

model the protocol flows of both aggregation methods. In the Attestation phase, there are only three participating entities. The specific formal modeling is as follows:

$$\text{Verifier}_{tpm-tee} \equiv (\hat{P}, K_{PV}, K_V)[$$

new n, PCR_{sel} ;
 $request := \text{symenc}(n, PCE_{sel}), K_{PV}$;
send $\hat{V}, \hat{P}, request$;

receive $\hat{P}, \hat{V}, EncReport$;
 $totalReport := \text{symdec}(EncReport, K_{PV})$;
verify $totalReport, AIK_{pub}$;
 $token := \text{sign}(type, totalReport, expireTime,$
 $policy), K_V^{-1}$;
 $tokenInfo := \text{symenc}(token, K_{PV})$;
send $\hat{V}, \hat{P}, tokenInfo$;

$$]_V()$$

$$\text{TPM}_{tpm-tee} \equiv (\hat{E}, \hat{V}, K_{PV}, K_{PE})[$$

receive $\hat{V}, \hat{P}, request$;
 $n, PCR_{sel} := \text{symdec}(request, K_{PV})$;
 $reportRequest := \text{symenc}(n, K_{PE})$;
send $\hat{P}, \hat{E}, reportRequest$;

receive $\hat{E}, \hat{P}, TEEEncReport$;
 $TEEReport := \text{symdec}(TEEEncReport, K_{PE})$;
 $totalReport := \text{sign}(PCR_{sel}, n,$
 $TEEReport), AIK^{-1}$;
 $EncReport := \text{symenc}(totalReport, K_{PV})$;
send $\hat{P}, \hat{V}, EncReport$;

receive $\hat{V}, \hat{P}, tokenInfo$;
 $token := \text{symdec}(tokenInfo, K_{PV})$;

$$]_P(token)$$

$$\text{TEE}_{tpm-tee} \equiv (\hat{P}, K_{PE})[$$

receive $\hat{P}, \hat{E}, reportRequest$;
 $TEETCB := (OVMF, GuestKernel,$
 $GuestInitrd, KernelCmdline)$;
 $TEEReport := \text{sign}(TEETCB, VECK^{-1})$;
 $TEEEncReport := \text{symenc}(TEEReport, K_{PE})$;
send $\hat{E}, \hat{P}, TEEEncReport$;

$$]_E()$$

$$\text{Verifier}_{tee-tpm} \equiv (\hat{E}, K_{EV}, K_V)[$$

new n, PCR_{sel} ;
 $request := \text{symenc}(n, PCR_{sel}), K_{EV}$;
send $\hat{V}, \hat{E}, request$;

receive $\hat{E}, \hat{V}, EncReport$;
 $totalReport := \text{symdec}(EncReport, K_{EV})$;
verify $totalReport, VCEK_{pub}$;
 $token := \text{sign}(type, totalReport, expireTime,$
 $policy), K_V^{-1}$;
 $tokenInfo := \text{symenc}(token, K_{EV})$;
send $\hat{V}, \hat{E}, tokenInfo$;

$$]_V()$$

$$\text{TPM}_{tee-tpm} \equiv (\hat{E}, K_{PE})[$$

receive $\hat{E}, \hat{P}, quoteRequest$;
 $n, PCR_{sel} := \text{symdec}(quoteRequest, K_{PE})$;
 $TPMReport := \text{sign}(PCRs, AIK^{-1})$;
 $TPMEncReport := \text{symenc}(TPMReport, K_{PE})$;
send $\hat{P}, \hat{E}, TPMEncReport$;

$$]_P()$$

$$\text{TEE}_{tee-tpm} \equiv (\hat{V}, \hat{P}, K_{PV}, K_{EV})[$$

receive $\hat{V}, \hat{E}, request$;
 $n, PCR_{sel} := \text{symdec}(request, K_{EV})$;
 $quoteRequest := \text{symenc}(n, PCR_{sel}), K_{PE}$;
send $\hat{E}, \hat{P}, quoteRequest$;

receive $\hat{P}, \hat{E}, TPMEncReport$;
 $TPMReport := \text{symdec}(TPMEncReport, K_{PE})$;
 $TEETCB := (OVMF, GuestKernel,$
 $GuestInitrd, KernelCmdline)$;
 $totalReport := \text{sign}(TEETCB, TPMReport,$
 $n), VCEK^{-1}$;
 $EncReport := \text{symenc}(totalReport, K_{EV})$;
send $\hat{E}, \hat{V}, EncReport$;

receive $\hat{V}, \hat{E}, tokenInfo$;
 $token := \text{symdec}(tokenInfo, K_{EV})$;

$$]_E(token)$$

During the execution of the Attestation phase, the Verifier performs reasoning according to the steps described above: 1) Through (1) - (3), in light of the actions it has executed, \hat{V} is capable of deducing that the sent message includes a token encrypted with K_{PV} , and this token is generated by being signed by its own private key. 2) In the range of (4) - (6), considering that \hat{P} possesses the token, and the held token is produced after being signed by \hat{V} , and \hat{V} has transmitted the message containing the token. 3) (7) - (9) imply that given the circumstance that \hat{V} itself has not performed decryption, then according to symmetric encryption, it can be determined that the decrypting entity is \hat{P} . 4) Based on the fact that \hat{P} can decrypt the encrypted

message by \hat{V} , then from (9), it can be inferred that \hat{P} holds the symmetric encryption key. 5) Synthesizing the above inferences, it can be concluded in (10) that if \hat{P} holds the token, then \hat{P} holds the encryption key of the secure channel with \hat{V} , and the token is issued by being signed by \hat{V} .

Proof of Theorem 2:

- (1) AA1, P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{tokenInfo})$
- (2) (1), AR1 $\top[\text{tokenInfo} := \text{symenc } \text{token}, K_{PV}; \text{token} := \text{sign}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}), K_V^{-1};] \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy})))$
- (3) (2), P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy})))$
- (4) (2) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}))$
- (5) (4), VER $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy})) \supset \text{Send}(V, \text{msg}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{msg}, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}))$
- (6) (2), (4), (5) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Send}(V, \text{msg}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{msg}, \text{token})$
- (7) (2) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset X, \exists X. \text{Dec}(\text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{token})) \supset \hat{X} = \hat{P} \vee \hat{X} = \hat{V}$
- (8) (7), AA1, P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \neg \text{Dec}(V, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{token})) \supset \hat{X} \neq \hat{V}$
- (9) (7), (8) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Dec}(P, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{token}))$
- (10) (9), Γ_1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Honest}(\hat{P}) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Has}(\hat{P}, K_{PV})$
- (11) (6), (9), (10) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Honest}(\hat{P}) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset \text{Has}(\hat{P}, K_{PV}) \wedge \text{Send}(V, \text{msg}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{msg}, \text{token})$

Proof of Theorem 3:

- (1) AA1, P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Receive}(V, \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{EncReport})$
- (2) (1), AR1 $\top[\text{EncReport} := \text{symenc } \text{totalReport}, K_{PV}; \text{totalReport} := \text{sign}(PCR_{sel}, n, TEEReport), AIK^{-1};] \text{Receive}(V, \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(PCR_{sel}, n, TEEReport)))$
- (3) (2), AR1 $\top[\text{request} := \text{symenc}(n, PCE_{sel}), K_{PV};]_V \text{Receive}(V, \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(\text{Dec}(P, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{request})), TEEReport)))$
- (4) (3), P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Receive}(V, \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(\text{Dec}(P, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{request})), TEEReport)))$
- (5) (4) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{request}) \supset \exists X. \text{Send}(X, \hat{X}, \hat{P}, \text{request}) \supset \hat{X} = \hat{P} \vee \hat{X} = \hat{V}$

Continuation of the proof of Theorem 3:

- (6) (5), AA1, P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \neg \text{Encrypt}(P, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(n, PCR_{sel})) \supset \hat{X} \neq \hat{P}$
- (7) (6), Γ_2 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Receive}(P, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{request}) > \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) > \text{Receive}(V, \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{EncReport})$
- (8) AA1, P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{tokenInfo})$
- (9) (8) $\top[\text{tokenInfo} := \text{symenc } \text{token}, K_{PV}; \text{token} := \text{sign}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}), K_V^{-1};]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy})))$
- (10) (9) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Sign}(V, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{token}))$
- (11) (7), (10) $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Honest}(\hat{P}) \wedge \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(\text{totalReport})) \wedge \text{Has}(\hat{P}, \text{token}) \supset (\text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{request}) > \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}))) \wedge \text{Sign}(V, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{token}))$

Proof of Theorem 4:

- (1) AA1, P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{X}, \hat{P}, \text{request})$
- (2) (1), SEC $\top[\text{new } n, PCR_{sel}; \text{request} := \text{symenc}(n, PCR_{sel}), K_{PV};]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{Encrypt}(V, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(n, PCR_{sel})))$
- (3) (2), P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{Encrypt}(V, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(n, PCR_{sel})))$
- (4) (3), FS1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{FirstSend}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{request}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{request}, n)$
- (5) AA1 $\top[\text{Verifier}_{attest}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{tokenInfo})$
- (6) (5), AR2 $\top[\text{verify } \text{totalReport}, AIK_{pub}; \text{token} := \text{sign}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}), K_V^{-1}; \text{tokenInfo} := \text{symenc } \text{token}, K_{PV};]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{Encrypt}(V, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{Sign}(P, (\text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{totalReport}, \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}))))))$
- (7) (6), AR3 $\top[\text{receive } \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{EncReport}; \text{totalReport} := \text{symdec } \text{EncReport}, K_{PV};]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{Encrypt}(V, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{Sign}(V, (\text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{Dec}(V, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{EncReport})), \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}))))))$
- (8) (7), VER $\top[\text{totalReport} := \text{sign}(PCR_{sel}, n, TEEReport), AIK^{-1}; \text{EncReport} := \text{symenc } \text{totalReport}, K_{PV}; \text{send } \hat{P}, \hat{V}, \text{EncReport};]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{Dec}(V, \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{Dec}(P, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(PCR_{sel}, n, TEEReport))), \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}))))))$
- (9) (8), P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}]_V \text{Send}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{Dec}(V, \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{K_V^{-1}}(\text{type}, \text{Dec}(P, \text{ENC}_{K_{PV}}(\text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{AIK^{-1}}(PCR_{sel}, n, TEEReport))), \text{expireTime}, \text{policy}))))))$
- (10) (9), Γ_3 $\top[\text{Verifier}]_V \text{Verify}(V, \text{totalReport}, AIK_{pub}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{totalReport}, n);$

Continuation of the proof of Theorem 4:

- (11) (10),P1 $\top[\text{Verifier}]_V \text{Verify}(V, \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{\text{AIK}^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}))) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{totalReport}, n)$
- (12) (4), (11) $\top[\text{Verifier}]_V (\text{FirstSend}(V, \hat{V}, \hat{P}, \text{request}) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{request}, n) \wedge (\text{Verify}(V, \text{Sign}(P, \text{SIG}_{\text{AIK}^{-1}}(\text{totalReport}))) \wedge \text{Contains}(\text{totalReport}, n)))$

C. Proverif formal security analysis

1) *Formal Modeling of Protocol Flow:* The flow of the composite attestation protocol consists of two phases: the initialization phase and the proof phase.

1) Modeling for the initialization phase

The initialization phase protocol includes two relatively independent parts: the initialization phase of TEE and the initialization phase of TPM.

(1) Modeling for the Initialization phase of TEE

The initialization phase of TEE involves three parties: OCA, TEE, and Verifier. The flow is as follows.

- 1) TEE generates the key VCEK, which is signed by ASK (AMD SEV Key), and ASK is signed by ARK (AMD Root Key), forming a certificate chain. To simplify the modeling, the certificate chain is modeled as a signature on public keys, which means that the VCEK certificate chain can be represented as: $\text{cert}_{\text{chain}} = \text{sign}_{\text{ARK}}(\text{ASK}_{\text{pub}}) \parallel \text{sign}_{\text{ASK}}(\text{VCEK}_{\text{pub}})$. TEE sends this certificate chain, $\text{cert}_{\text{chain}}$, to OCA.
- 2) OCA receives $\text{cert}_{\text{chain}}$, verifies the validity of the certificate chain, and after successful verification, generates $\text{cert}_{\text{VCEK}} = \text{sign}_{\text{OCA}}(\text{VCEK}_{\text{pub}})$, and then sends $\text{cert}_{\text{VCEK}}$ to TEE.
- 3) TEE receives $\text{cert}_{\text{VCEK}}$ and sends both $\text{cert}_{\text{VCEK}}$ and VCEK_{pub} to Verifier.
- 4) Verifier receives $\text{cert}_{\text{VCEK}}$ and VCEK_{pub} , verifies them, and if successful, completes the TEE initialization.

The following is the ProVerif script 1 for the OCA subprocess in the TEE initialization phase.

Algorithm 1 TEE_init_OCA

```
1: Input: oca_priv : sskkey, ark_pub : spkey
2: Output: oca_vcek_cert: bitstring
3: in(c_oca_tee, (vcek_cert_chain: bitstring, vcek_pub: spkey))
4: let (sign1, sign2) = vcek_cert_chain
5: let ask_pub = check_sign(sign1, ark_pub)
6: let vcek_pub = check_sign(sign2, ask_pub)
7: oca_vcek_cert = sign(vcek_pub, oca_priv)
8: out(c_oca_tee, oca_vcek_cert)
```

The following is the ProVerif script 2 for the TEE subprocess in the initialization phase of TEE.

Algorithm 2 TEE_init_TEE

```
1: Input: vcek_priv : sskkey, vcek_cert_chain : bitstring
2: let vcek_pub = spk(vcek_priv)
3: out(c_oca_tee, (vcek_cert_chain, vcek_pub))
4: in(c_oca_tee, oca_vcek_cert: bitstring)
5: out(c_tee_Verifier, (oca_vcek_cert, vcek_pub))
```

The following is the ProVerif script 3 for the Verifier subprocess in the initialization phase of TEE.

Algorithm 3 TEE_init_Verifier

```
1: Input: oca_pub : spkey
2: in(c_tee_verifier, (oca_vcek_cert : bitstring, vcek_pub : spkey))
3: let (vcek_pub) = check_sign(oca_vcek_cert, oca_pub)
4: halt 0
```

(2) TPM initialization phase protocol modeling

The participants in the initialization phase of TPM include OCA, TPM, and Verifier. The protocol flow is as follows:

- 1) TPM generates the seed key $EPSeed$; the Endorsement Key EK is generated by the function $\text{TPM2_CreatePrimary}$. The Attestation Identity Key AIK is then generated using EK . The key EK is certified by a trusted third-party CA, and the certificate is given by $\text{cert}_{EK} = \text{sign}_{\text{trust}_{ca}}(EK_{\text{pub}})$. TPM sends AIK_{pub} , EK_{pub} , and cert_{EK} to OCA.
- 2) Upon receiving AIK_{pub} , EK_{pub} , and cert_{EK} , OCA verifies the legitimacy of EK_{pub} by validating cert_{EK} . After successful verification, OCA randomly generates a nonce n and creates the challenge:
 $\text{challenge} = \text{MakeCredential}(n, H(AIK_{\text{pub}}), EK_{\text{pub}})$ where H is a hash function. OCA sends the challenge to TPM.
- 3) TPM receives the challenge and generates $n' = \text{ActivateCredential}(m, H(AIK_{\text{pub}}), EK)$, where m is the measurement data. TPM sends n' to OCA.
- 4) Upon receiving n' , OCA compares it with the previously generated nonce n . If they match, OCA generates $\text{cert}_{AIK} = \text{sign}_{\text{OCA}}(AIK_{\text{pub}})$ and sends cert_{AIK} to TPM.
- 5) TPM receives cert_{AIK} and sends both cert_{AIK} and AIK_{pub} to the Verifier.
- 6) The Verifier receives cert_{AIK} and AIK_{pub} , performs verification, and upon successful validation, the TPM initialization is completed.

2) Modeling for the attestation phase

There are two optional protocols: Attestation-tee-tpm, which composites the SEV report into the TPM Quote, and Attestation-tpm-tee, which composites the TPM Quote into the SEV report.

(1) Modeling for Attestation-TEE-TPM

The participants in the protocol of Attestation-TEE-TPM include TEE, TPM, and Verifier. The protocol flow is as follows:

- 1) The Verifier randomly generates a nonce and selects PCR values as parameters, creating a proof request $\text{AttestationRequest}(\text{nonce}, \text{PCRsel})$, and sends it to TPM.
- 2) Upon receiving the proof request, TPM sends a $\text{GuestReportRequest}$ to TEE.
- 3) The launch measurement value of TEE, denoted as TEE_TCB , is calculated as:
 $\text{TEE_TCB} = \text{OVMF} \parallel \text{GuestKernel} \parallel \text{GuestInitrd} \parallel \text{KernelCmdline}$

Using TEE_TCB , TEE generates the TEE_Report and signs it using VCEK, i.e., $TEE_Report = \text{sign}_{VCEK}(TEE_TCB)$. TEE sends the TEE_Report to TPM.

- 4) TPM executes the $TPM2_CCQuote$, using $PCRsel$, n , and TEE_Report as parameters to generate the composite report $Total_Report$, i.e.,
 $Total_Report = TPM2_CCQuote_{AIK}(PCRsel, nonce, TEE_Report)$,
 and sends it to Verifier.
- 5) Upon receiving the $Total_Report$, Verifier verifies the integrity of the TPM report using AIK_{pub} and checks that the TEE_Report is signed by VCEK. If the verification is successful, the Verifier generates a token, $token = \text{Sign}_{AS}(\text{Type}, Total_Report, \text{ExpireTime}, \text{Policy})$.
 Then sends the token to TPM.
- 6) Upon receiving the token, the Attestation is completed.

(2) Modeling for Attestation-TPM-TEE

The participants in the protocol of Attestation-TPM-TEE include TEE, TPM, and Verifier. The protocol flow is as follows:

- 1) Verifier randomly generates a nonce and selects PCR values as parameters, creating a proof request $AttestationRequest(nonce, PCRsel)$, and sends it to TEE.
- 2) TEE generates a request $TPMQuoteRequest(nonce, PCRsel)$, and sends it to TPM.
- 3) TPM generates the TPM_Report as $TPM_Report = \text{Quote}(PCRsel)$, and sends it to TEE.
- 4) Using VCEK, TEE signs TEE_TCB , TPM_Report , and nonce to generate the composite report $Total_Report$, i.e.,
 $Total_Report = \text{Sign}_{VCEK}(TEE_TCB, TPM_Report, nonce)$,
 and sends it to Verifier.
- 5) Upon receiving the $Total_Report$, the Verifier checks that the report is signed by VCEK and ensures that the TPM_Report was issued by TPM. If the verification is successful, the Verifier generates a token, $token = \text{Sign}_{AS}(\text{Type}, Total_Report, \text{ExpireTime}, \text{Policy})$,
 and sends the token to TEE.
- 6) Upon receiving the token, the Attestation finishes.

2) *Threat Model*: The composite attestation protocol includes several communication channels:

- $channel_{OCA-TEE}$, the channel from OCA to TEE;
- $channel_{OCA-TPM}$, the channel from OCA to TPM;
- $channel_{TEE-TPM}$, the channel from TEE to TPM;
- $channel_{TEE-Verifier}$, the channel from TEE to Verifier;
- $channel_{TPM-Verifier}$, the channel from TPM to Verifier.

Among these channels, $channel_{OCA-TEE}$, $channel_{OCA-TPM}$, and $channel_{TEE-TPM}$ are considered secure channels, meaning that there are no adversarial

attackers. However, there are adversaries capable of carrying out Dolev-Yao attacks on $channel_{TEE-Verifier}$ and $channel_{TPM-Verifier}$.

3) Security Objectives: 1. Correctness of OCA Certificate Issuance

After the execution of the initialization phase, if an entity receives a certificate (either $cert_{VCEK}$ or $cert_{AIK}$, it implies that the certificate was issued by OCA, and the entity holds a legitimate endorsement key (either EK or $VCEK$).

The formal specification of this security objective is as follows:

query $k : \text{spkey}$;
 $\text{inj-event}(\text{issue_cert}(k)) \Rightarrow \text{inj-event}(\text{request_cert}(k))$.

2. Correctness of Token Issuance

After the completion of the attestation protocol, if an entity possesses a token, it implies that the token was issued by the Verifier, and the entity's $Total_Report$ has been verified as correct.

The formal specification of this security objective is as follows:

query $n : \text{nonce}$;
 $\text{inj-event}(\text{issue_token}(n)) \Rightarrow \text{inj-event}(\text{request_token}(n))$.

4) *Integrity of the Token*: If an entity generates a attestation report, it implies that the entity has previously received a attestation request from Verifier, and the token was issued by Verifier.

The formal specification of this security objective is as follows:

query $n : \text{nonce}$;
 $\text{inj-event}(\text{check_token}(n)) \Rightarrow \text{inj-event}(\text{request_attestation}(n))$.